

Apparent brightness of Earth seen from Mars for 1976-2014 (local extrema)

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An observer stays in space ship that circles around Mars.

Explanations:

mag =stellar magnitude ,

°=degree,

'= angular minutes ,

"= angular seconds

AE= astronomical unit=149598500 km

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance from Earth to Mars [AE]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance from Earth to Sun [AE]
9.3.- 22.3.1976	-1.75	43-51 increasing	1.18-1.32 increasing	36.93-37.22 increasing	13.3-14.9 decreasing	0.99-1.00 increasing
21.7.- 2.9.1976	-1.49	88-96 increasing	2.29-2.47 increasing	15.77-23.35 decreasing	7.1-7.7 decreasing	1.00-1.01 decreasing
28.9.-17.10. 1977	-2.00	51-60 decreasing	1.19-1.34 decreasing	40.45-40.67 decreasing	13.1-14.8 increasing	0.99-1.01 decreasing
21.1.- 22.1.1978	weaker than +6.00	<1	0.65	2.65	27.1	0.98
20.4.- 16.5.1978	-1.70	47-59 increasing	1.26-1.50 increasing	36.89-37.04 decreasing	11.7-14.0 decreasing	1.00-1.02 increasing
12.8.- 11.9.1978	-1.59	84-91 increasing	2.12-2.26 increasing	22.34-27.09 decreasing	7.8-8.3 decreasing	1.00-1.02 decreasing
17.1.- 17.3.1979	-1.72	98-100 decreasing	2.33-2.39 decreasing	0.83-8.87 increasing	7.4-7.5 increasing	0.98-1.00 increasing
19.6.- 23.6.1979	-1.67	91-93 decreasing	2.18-2.20 decreasing	22.13-22.67 increasing	8.0-8.1 increasing	1.02
7.11.-12.11. 1979	-1.82	56-59 decreasing	1.40-1.45 decreasing	37.37-37.49 increasing	12.1-12.6 increasing	0.99-1.00 decreasing
25.2.1980	weaker than +6.00	<1	0.68	2.60	25.9	0.99
10.6.- 19.6.1980	-1.80	54-59 increasing	1.35-1.43 increasing	38.68-38.84 decreasing	12.3-13.0 decreasing	1.01-1.02 increasing
17.8.- 19.10.1980	-1.75	76-89 increasing	1.81-2.09 increasing	25.49-33.93 decreasing	8.4-9.7 decreasing	0.99-1.02 decreasing
20.11.1980 - 1.1.1981	-1.77	93-97 increasing	2.17-2.27 increasing	14.21-20.72 decreasing	7.7-8.1 decreasing	0.98-1.00 decreasing
3.7.-5.8.1981	-1.55	93-97 decreasing	2.33-2.41 decreasing	14.31-19.50 increasing	7.3-7.5 increasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
3.12.- 25.12.1981	-1.73	50-61 decreasing	1.35-1.57 decreasing	35.44-36.22 increasing	11.2-13.0 increasing	0.98-0.99 decreasing
31.3.1982	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.64	1.83	27.5	1.00
25.7.1982	-2.01	56	1.25	41.95	14.1	1.02
10.7.- 22.8.1983	-1.47	96-100 decreasing	2.49-2.57 decreasing	6.59-14.17 increasing	6.8-7.1 increasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
26.1.- 7.2.1984	-1.76	46-52 decreasing	1.23-1.36 decreasing	36.60-36.77 increasing	12.9-14.3 increasing	0.98-0.99 increasing
11.5.1984	weaker than +11.00	<1	0.54	0.09	32.6	1.01
15.8.- 2.9.1984	-2.33	44-52 increasing	0.91-1.02 increasing	44.86-45.61 increasing	17.2-19.3 decreasing	1.00-1.02 decreasing
21.7.- 18.8.1985	-1.42	99-100 decreasing	2.63-2.65 decreasing	0.93-6.13 increasing	6.6-6.7 increasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
8.4-19.4.1986	-1.99	34-39 decreasing	0.86-0.97 decreasing	38.77-39.53 decreasing	18.1-20.5 increasing	1.00-1.01 increasing
9.7.-	weaker than	<1	0.41	3.94	42.9	1.02

10.7.1986	+4.00					
28.9.- 13.10.1986	-2.50	33-39 increasing	0.67-0.77 increasing	43.13-44.70 increasing	22.8-26.3 decreasing	0.99-1.01 decreasing
30.7.- 10.8.1987	-1.40	99-100 increasing	2.65-2.68 increasing	2.97-5.17 decreasing	6.6	1.01-1.02 decreasing
29.6.- 16.7.1988	-2.48	30-37 decreasing	0.62-0.73 decreasing	42.46-44.69 decreasing	24.1-28.4 increasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
28.9.1988	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.40	3.26	44.0	1.00
13.12.-26.12. 1988	-2.12	33-40 increasing	0.81-0.93 increasing	38.99-40.13 increasing	18.9-21.7 decreasing	0.98-0.99 decreasing
13.7.- 31.8.1989	-1.42	95-100 increasing	2.52-2.65 increasing	5.83-15.31 decreasing	6.6-7.0 decreasing	1.00-1.02 decreasing
14.8.- 5.9.1990	-2.40	41-50 decreasing	0.82-0.95 decreasing	44.66-46.53 decreasing	18.5-21.4 increasing	1.00-1.02 decreasing
27.11.1990	weaker than +8.00	<1	0.52	0.96	33.8	0.99
17.2.- 4.3.1991	-1.81	40-49 increasing	1.09-1.25 increasing	37.17-37.68 increasing	14.1-16.1 decreasing	0.99
23.7.- 30.8.1991	-1.46	91-97 increasing	2.38-2.53 increasing	13.47-20.48 decreasing	7.0-7.4 decreasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
15.9.- 6.10.1992	-2.10	49-58 decreasing	1.10-1.24 decreasing	41.87-42.47 decreasing	14.2-16.0 increasing	1.00-1.01 decreasing
7.1.-8.1.1993	weaker than +6.00	<1	0.63	2.47	27.9	0.98
3.4.- 27.4.1993	-1.70	45-57 increasing	1.23-1.47 increasing	36.78-36.82 increasing	12.0-14.3 decreasing	1.00-1.01 increasing
8.8.- 28.8.1993	-1.54	87-91 increasing	2.22-2.31 increasing	21.57-24.80 decreasing	7.6-7.9 decreasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
24.10-31.10. 1994	-1.88	55-59 decreasing	1.34-1.41 decreasing	38.46-38.55 increasing	12.5-13.1 increasing	0.99-1.00 decreasing
11.2.- 12.2.1995	weaker than +6.00	<1	0.68	2.70	25.9	0.99
16.5.- 16.6.1995	-1.74	49-63 increasing	1.27-1.54 increasing	37.36-37.87 decreasing	11.4-13.8 decreasing	1.01-1.02 increasing
10.8.- 27.9.1995	-1.68	78-89 increasing	1.91-2.14 increasing	25.16-31.93 decreasing	8.2-9.2 decreasing	1.00-1.02 decreasing
19.12.1995 - 30.1.1996	-1.74	97-100 increasing	2.31-2.36 increasing	5.37-12.01 decreasing	7.5-7.6 decreasing	0.98-0.99 increasing
11.6.- 9.8.1996	-1.60	89-97 decreasing	2.21-2.36 decreasing	14.83-23.56 increasing	7.5-8.0 increasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
16.11.-12.12. 1996	-1.75	51-63 decreasing	1.34-1.59 decreasing	35.67-36.51 increasing	11.1-13.1 increasing	0.98-0.99 decreasing
17.3.1997	weaker than +6.00	<1	0.66	2.22-2.23 decreasing	26.6	1.00
10.7.1997	-1.92	57	1.32	40.53-40.54 decreasing	13.3	1.02
2.7.- 22.8.1998	-1.50	94-99 decreasing	2.42-2.52 decreasing	8.60-17.36 increasing	7.0-7.3 increasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
30.12.1998 - 21.1.1999	-1.73	47-58 decreasing	1.28-1.51 decreasing	35.69 - 36.19 increasing	11.6-13.7 increasing	0.98-0.99 increasing
24.4.1999	weaker than +9.00	<1	0.58	0.85	30.3	1.01
2.8.- 26.8.1999	-2.20	48-57 increasing	1.01-1.16 increasing	43.86-44.28 increasing	15.2-17.4 decreasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
10.7.- 28.8.2000	-1.44	97-100 decreasing	2.57-2.62 decreasing	1.64-10.93 increasing	6.7-6.8 increasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
5.3.- 19.3.2001	-1.86	38-46 decreasing	1.01-1.17 decreasing	37.83-38.23 decreasing	15.0-17.4 increasing	0.99-1.00 increasing
13.6.2001	weaker than +6.00	<1	0.46	2.26	38.2	1.01
7.9.- 23.9.2001	-2.49	37-44 increasing	0.74-0.84 increasing	44.63-45.96 increasing	20.9-23.8 decreasing	1.00-1.01 decreasing
14.7.- 27.8.2002	-1.41	99-100 increasing	2.64-2.67 increasing	3.32-5.36 decreasing	6.6-6.7 decreasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
2.6.- 14.6.2003	-2.31	29-35 decreasing	0.66-0.75 decreasing	40.70-42.21 decreasing	23.5-26.6 increasing	1.01-1.02 increasing
28.8.- 29.8.2003	weaker than +3.00	<1	0.37	4.84	47.5	1.01

11.11.-27.11.2003	-2.30	30-38 increasing	0.70-0.83 increasing	40.08-41.77 increasing	21.2-25.1 decreasing	0.98-0.99 decreasing
15.7.-27.8.2004	-1.41	96-100 increasing	2.57-2.67 increasing	3.85-12.37 decreasing	6.6-6.8 decreasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
1.8.-19.8.2005	-2.50	37-45 decreasing	0.72-0.83 decreasing	44.81-46.80 decreasing	21.2-24.4 increasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
7.11.2005	weaker than +10.00	<1	0.47	0.31	37.4	0.99
23.1.-10.2.2006	-1.90	36-46 increasing	0.98-1.16 increasing	37.53-38.46 increasing	15.2-17.9 decreasing	0.98-0.99 increasing
19.7.-31.8.2006	-1.44	92-98 increasing	2.44-2.59 increasing	10.49-18.53 decreasing	6.8-7.2 decreasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
12.9.-18.9.2007	-2.22	49-53 decreasing	1.04-1.09 decreasing	43.73-44.08 decreasing	16.1-16.9 increasing	1.00-1.01 decreasing
24.12.2007	weaker than +6.00	<1	0.59	2.09	29.8	0.98
21.3.-31.3.2008	-1.73	45-51 increasing	1.23-1.34 increasing	36.93-37.09 increasing	13.1-14.3 decreasing	0.99-1.00 increasing
20.7.-10.9.2008	-1.51	86-95 increasing	2.22-2.44 increasing	16.18-25.06 decreasing	7.2-7.9 decreasing	1.00-1.02 decreasing
3.10.-25.10.2009	-1.95	51-61 decreasing	1.23-1.39 decreasing	39.66-39.71 decreasing	12.7-14.3 increasing	0.99-1.00 decreasing
29.1.-30.1.2010	weaker than +6.00	<1	0.66-0.67 increasing	2.71	26.3-26.6 decreasing	0.99
30.4.-26.5.2010	-1.71	48-60	1.28-1.51 increasing	37.06-37.30 decreasing	11.6-13.7 decreasing	1.01
4.8.-17.9.2010	-1.62	81-90 increasing	2.01-2.22 increasing	23.25-29.86 decreasing	7.9-8.8 decreasing	1.00-1.02 decreasing
31.12.2010 - 6.3.2011	-1.72	99-100 increasing	2.36-2.38 decreasing	4.75-5.76 decreasing	7.4-7.5 increasing	0.98-1.00 increasing
28.5.-31.7.2011	-1.65	88-96 decreasing	2.13-2.29 decreasing	16.83-25.62 increasing	7.7-8.3 increasing	1.01-1.02 increasing
7.11.-26.11.2011	-1.79	53-62 decreasing	1.36-1.53 decreasing	36.60-37.09 increasing	11.5-12.9 increasing	0.99
3.3.-4.3.2012	weaker than +6.00	<1	0.67	2.49	26.3	0.99
9.6.-14.7.2012	-1.83	50-65 increasing	1.25-1.52 increasing	38.54-39.28 decreasing	11.6-14.1 decreasing	1.01-1.02 increasing
3.7.-11.8.2013	-1.53	93-98 decreasing	2.36-2.46 decreasing	12.30-18.71 increasing	7.1-7.5 increasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
18.12.-30.12.2013	-1.73	51-58 decreasing	1.38-1.50 decreasing	35.77-36.15 increasing	11.7-12.7 increasing	0.98-0.99 decreasing
8.4.-9.4.2014	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.62	1.53	28.4	1.00
23.7.-12.8.2014	-2.08	51-59 increasing	1.13-1.26 increasing	42.67-42.68 decreasing	14.0-15.6 decreasing	1.01-1.02 decreasing
31.12.2014	-1.88	88	1.97	27.69	8.9	0.98

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